

**Global Employee Relations: Organizational Learning
in the Transnational Organization with a Hybrid
(Virtual Offsite / Traditional 'Brick and Mortar') Workforce**

An Analytical Paper

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Web Site: <http://zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles>

Twitter: @ResearchZeller

Blog: DZellerResearch.blogspot.com

B.S. Organizational Leadership,
The Pennsylvania State University
M.P.S. Human Resources and Employment Relations
The Pennsylvania State University

Abstract

In an analytical paper, the author poses a question, collects relevant data from other researchers, analyzes the data from their viewpoints, then concludes with a summation of findings and a suggested framework for further study (Paper Pile, 2020; Personal Writer, 2008). The author maintains a neutral position; the focus is “on the findings and conclusions of other researchers” (Paper Pile, 2020). The objective of this analytical paper is to collect then analyze the findings from a variety of sources on global employee relations, the transnational model of organizations, the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce, and organizational learning. The questions are: What is the relationship, if any, between global employee relations and organizational learning? Is that relationship being redefined by the increase in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce in the transnational organization?

****Analytical papers “include information from a range of sources; the focus is on analyzing the different viewpoints represented from a factual rather than an opinionated standpoint” (Personal Writer, 2008).**

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Introduction

In 1966, Alan Fox termed the phrase ‘Industrial Relations’. Originally, Fox developed two perspectives: unitary and pluralist. In the 1970s, Fox added a third perspective, radical or Marxist (Heery, 2016, p. 2). Subsequently, ‘Industrial Relations’ transitioned to the term ‘Employee Relations’. Though there are different viewpoints regarding their definitions and applications, industrial relations is the term generally used to describe the collective voice; e.g. unions; between employers and employees; and employee relations is concerned with communication with employees; involvement and participation of employees; conflicts; discipline and grievances procedures (Aylott, 2014, p. 11-12).

Additionally, the global market has introduced new and changing regulations and polycentric practices; thereby, making employee relations difficult to transfer (Zeller, 2016). Furthermore, the transferability of the different aspects of employee relations is political, involving numerous organizational actors with varying levels of influence; therefore, the organizational structure is a factor when transferring employee relations globally (Edwards, 2004, p. 392).

Bartlett and Ghoshal predict that, due to increased globalization, multinational organizations will need to embrace the transnational model (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 2009). The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this analytical paper, is described as having a high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation; with knowledge and innovation developed and distributed within the entire organization. The practice of knowledge sharing also recognizes the benefits gained from local responsiveness and adaptation.

Within the transnational model, another element to consider is the growing transition to a hybrid (traditional physical office / virtual off-site) workforce (Zeller, 2017). The concept of physical placement complicates the transnational model where operations are guided by local context as well as by “close cooperation and interdependence among its headquarters, operations, and international subsidiaries” (Zwass, 1998). Hence, regional regulations and preferences may not be identified or may be overlooked; alternatives may not be implemented; and the relevance of benefits for strategies and goals may be misunderstood or underestimated (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005).

In view of the fact that the hybrid work venues have changed where and the way that people work; at times, there is a disconnect between jobs, processes, and structure (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010). Research has also identified that, due to the expansion of those spatial boundaries, organizational knowledge sharing and learning is being challenged (Verbeke, Schultz, Greidanus, & Hambley, 2008). The physical location or spatial proximity is important as it is “interrelated in business practices” (Andersson & Mattsson, 2014, p. 2; Zeller, 2017, Fall). That influence of spatial proximity on business practices is relevant because “where knowledge is produced and where it circulates is integral to its effects”; e.g. knowledge sharing and organizational learning on jobs, processes, and structures (Kuss, 2015, p. 433; Zeller, 2017, Fall).

In an analytical paper, the author poses a question, collects relevant data from other researchers, analyzes the data from their viewpoints, then concludes with a summation of findings and a suggested framework for further study (Paper Pile, 2020; Personal Writer, 2008). The author maintains a neutral position; the focus is “on the findings and conclusions of other researchers” (Paper Pile, 2020). The objective of this analytical paper is to analyze the findings from a variety of sources on global employee relations, the transnational model of organizations, the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce, and organizational learning. The context is United States-based multinational

organizations with a transnational model. The questions are: What is the relationship, if any, between global employee relations and organizational learning? Is that relationship being redefined by the increase in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce in the transnational organization?

Definitions

Note that the following terms, employee relations, employment relationship, industrial relations, and labor relations are sometimes used interchangeably. For this paper, the definition of the term employee relations will be applied to the analysis.

Employee Relations: Concerns communication with employees; involvement and participation of employees; conflicts; discipline and grievances procedures (Aylott, 2014, p. 12). “Communications between management and employees concerning workplace decisions, grievances, conflicts, problem resolutions, unions, and issues of collective bargaining” (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Employment Relationship: Basically, “businesses could not survive without their employees, who enable them to provide goods and services to their customers and clients. The relationship through which this is carried out is known as the ‘employment relationship’” (Aylott, 2014, p. 17).

Industrial Relations: “Employer-employee relationships that are covered specifically under collective bargaining and industrial relation laws” (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Labor Relations: “The ongoing relationship between an employer and union members or other defined groups of employees” (YourDictionary.com, n.d.).

These two terms are also used interchangeably within research:

Organizational Learning: “the embedding of individual- and group-level learning in organizational structures and processes, achieved through reflecting on and modifying the norms and values embodied in established organizational processes and structures” (Hislop, 2009, 2013, p. 87).

(The) Learning Organization: According to Senge (1990), “...organizations where people continually expand their capacity to create the results they truly desire, where new and expansive patterns of thinking are nurtured, where collective aspiration is set free, and where people are continually learning to see the whole together” (Smith, 2001, 2007).

Additional definitions used in this paper:

Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’) Workforce: For this paper, a hybrid workforce will refer to a combination of physical and virtual workspace / scheduling in the transnational model.

Transnational Organizations: Based on Bartlett and Ghoshal’s models of globalization (1989), the transnational approach, selected for this research, invites the transfer of practices to, from and within the affiliates; parent organizations and subsidiaries are aware of their own role as well as the role of others. There is high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation; knowledge and innovation is developed and distributed within the entire organization. In the transnational model, the practice of knowledge sharing also recognizes the benefits gained from local responsiveness and

adaptation (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 2009).

Objective

The objective of an analytical paper is to collect relevant data from other researchers and to analyze the data from their viewpoints. In this paper, the relevant data is regarding global employee relations, the transnational model of organizations, the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce, and organizational learning. The conclusion is a summation of the findings and a suggested framework for further study.

Problem Statement

The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this analytical paper, is described as having a high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation; with knowledge and innovation developed and distributed within the entire organization. However, the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce has introduced changes where and how people work; hence, business functions ranging from human resource practices and policies; to business processes, management, and structure have been affected (Zeller, 2018, Spring). As the geographic boundaries of organizations and the spatial boundaries of a virtual / traditional workforce change; where knowledge is produced and where it circulates is also changing. Thus, organizational learning is challenged. Primarily, the globalization of organizations has contributed to the difficulties in transferring employee relations across regions. The questions are: What is the relationship, if any, between global employee relations and organizational learning? Is that relationship being redefined by the increase in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce in the transnational organization?

Analysis of Existing Viewpoints

In an analytical paper, the author poses a question. The questions for this analytical paper are: What is the relationship, if any, between global employee relations and organizational learning? Is that relationship being redefined by the increase in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce in the transnational organization? The conceptual framework is the United States-based transnational models of multinational organizations with a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce.

Then the findings, from a variety of sources, are analyzed from a factual standpoint. The topics of the findings in the following paragraphs include: Employee Relations: Development of Definitions and Applications; Employee Relations: Perspectives; the Transnational Model of Organizations; the Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional 'Brick and Mortar') Workforce; and Organizational Learning.

Employee Relations: Development of Definitions and Application

Basically, the term 'employee relations' has evolved from the term 'industrial relations'. In practice, there continues to be different points of view regarding the definitions and application of the terms. Blyton and Turnbull (1994) argued that though there is no strict distinction between the two terms; there is a "tendency to

focus the subjects inside different boundaries” (Leat, 2007, p. 5) In their view, industrial relations tends to view the “world of work as synonymous with the manufacturing sector”, with an emphasis on “trade unions, collective bargaining, and industrial action” (Leat, 2007, p.5). Notably, this sector is on the decline in many countries. On the other hand, Blyton and Turnbull (1994) contend that the broader view of employee relations includes the growing service sector and includes the non-union as well as the union relationships (Leat, 2007, p. 5).

Furthermore, Blyton and Turnbull’s view (1994) identifies a difference between employee relations and the “individual and individual employment relationship” covered by personnel / human resource management (Leat, 2007, p.6)

Marchington and Wilkinson (1996) have suggested three reasons for the evolution of the differences in the terms (Leat, 2007, p. 5). One is the fashionable usage of employee relations. The second is the increased use by practitioners “concerned with the regulation of relations (collective and individual) between employer and employee” (Leat, 2007, p. 5). And, third, employee relations “tend to focus on management and management issues”, emphasizing “the way things are as opposed to the way things were” (Leat, 2007, p. 5). Overall, Marchington and Wilkinson (1996) see employee relations including both individual relations covered by personnel / human resource management and the collective relations between employer and employee (Leat, 2007, p. 6).

“In their text for the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), the professional body for personnel and human resource management in the United Kingdom,” Gennard and Judge (2002) basically adopted Marchington and Wilkinson’s (1996) managerial stance (Leat, 2007, p. 5). In part, Gennard and Judge (2002) define employee relations as:

“...a study of the rules, regulations and agreements by which employees are managed both as individuals and as a collective group, the priority given to the individual as opposed to the collective relationship varying from company to company depending on the values of management. As such it is concerned with how to gain people’s commitment to the achievement of an organization’s business goals and objectives in a number of different situations...” (Leat, 2007, p. 6).

Employee Relations: Perspectives

As defined, “a perspective is a way of looking at something, not the thing itself”; e.g. “it is not the system or form of organization” (Leat, 2007, p. 16). Frames of reference or perspectives are complex formulations that “rest on underlying assumptions about the interest of workers and their employers, which give rise, on the one hand, to formal ideologies; normative positions for evaluating the present and shaping the future. And, on the other hand, they generate theoretical models of the employment relationship, which offer explanations of institutions, behaviors, and outcomes, and can be weighed and tested through empirical research” (Heery, 2016, p. 5).

In 1966, Alan Fox applied the term ‘frame of reference’ to what is now commonly referred to as employee relations perspectives. Initially, Fox identified two perspectives, unitarist and pluralist. Later, Fox added the radical or Marxist perspective (Leat, 2007, p.16). Budd and Bhav (2008) described Fox’s frames of reference as “packages of values and assumptions pertaining to the interests of parties to the employment

relationship---that is, the needs, wants, and aspirations of employees, employers, and the state--and the degree to which these interests are compatible” (Heery, 2016, p. 2)

In the *Unitarist perspective*, “there is no conflict of interest between those supplying financial capital and their representatives, and those contributing their labor and skills on the other”; “the owners of capital and labor are joint partners to the common aim of efficient production” (Singh, 2011, p. 12). The employer and the managers are secure in their roles as decision-makers and their roles as authority figures are accepted by employees in a subordinate position (Singh, 2011, p. 12). In the 1980’s, the Unitarist perspective expanded to the Neo-Unitary approach, which is based on the market, management, and the employee as an individual (Singh, 2011, p. 12). In this perspective, the company endeavors to “create a shared corporate culture and shared corporate culture”; in which the focus is on customer service (Singh, 2011, p. 13).

In comparison, the *Pluralist perspective* “accepts conflict as inevitable but containable through various institutional arrangements” (Singh, 2011, p. 15). This perspective identifies with the frameworks of society and the political doctrine of sovereignty. For instance, this perspective recognizes that societies are composed of individuals and groups with “their own social values and each pursuing their own self-interests and objectives”; therefore, conflict is inevitable (Singh, 2011, p. 15). Fundamentally, that refers to the “political doctrine of sovereignty” doctrine which sustains that “somewhere in an independent political system, there must be a final authority whose decisions are definitive” (Singh, 2011, p. 15). Conversely, the pluralist approach recognizes that “there are no definitive decisions by final authorities; only continuous compromises” (Singh, 2011, p. 15). Basically, by accommodating these different groups through “negotiation, concession, and compromise”, “social and political changes take place constitutionally” (Singh, 2011, p. 15). Then, “organizations are held in balance by the agency of management” (Singh, 2011, p. 15).

The *Radical / Marxist approach* “reconciles those who are exploited to their condition, while leaving the structured inequality at the heart of the employment relationship unchanged” (Heery, 2016, p. 2) This perspective was the earliest to be subdivided, “with a distinction being drawn between a Marxist perspective, exemplified by the work of Richard Hyman (1975), and a ‘neo-Durkheimian’ position (Gilbert, 1986)” (Heery, 2016, p. 3). The neo-Durkheimian position concerned itself with “the decay of the traditional status order and the rise of instrumental collectivism through which unions strove to advance workers’ interests; thereby, generating an inflationary spiral in the process” (Heery, 2016, p. 3). In comparison, Richard Hyman, considered to be the unofficial founder of the Marxist perspective, “exposed the limitations of empiricism and offered a radical alternative to the prevailing functionalist theories of order and regulation” (Frege, Kelly, & McGovern, 2011, p. 212). “In the explicitly theoretical *Industrial Relations: A Marxist Introduction* (1975), Hyman offered an unorthodox Marxist framework built around the concepts of totality, change, contradiction, and practice; with contradiction being the “most distinctive contribution to the radical perspective” (Frege, Kelly, & McGovern, 2011, p. 214).

Basically, Fox’s “concepts of frame of reference” are “one of the few that have passed tests of ubiquity and longevity; being applied widely and continually”; however, “there have been two broad paths of descent”; the

application of the frames of reference to analyze the ideology of management and the concepts of the frames of reference from an academic view (Heery, 2016, p. 2-3). From those paths of descent, an array of frames of reference or perspectives have emerged. Essentially, they represent literal rebellions against the original frames of references; subdivisions; and new perspectives (Heery, 2016, p. 3).

For instance, Godard (2000) added five new frames of reference or perspectives: neoclassical, managerialist, orthodox pluralist, liberal reformist, and radical” (Heery, 2016, p. 3). Godard’s perspectives “involves a division into two of Fox’s unitary and pluralist perspectives” (Heery, 2016, p. 3). Godard draws on the unitary perspective to present a ‘managerialist viewpoint’ and the neo-classical or neo-conservative perspectives to align “worker and employer interests through market processes and economic incentives” (Heery, 2016, p. 3). In addition, Godard differentiates between the weak and strong aspects of the pluralist; leaning toward the neo-Durkheimian radicalists in “stressing elimination of inequalities and injustices” (Heery, 2016, p. 4).

Budd and Bhave (2008) isolate the constituents in the employment relationship in their four frames of reference: “egoist, unitarist, pluralist, and critical” (Heery, 2016, p. 4). The “central, normative principle” of the egoist perspective “is that beneficial outcomes, the maximization of utility, can be secured through the pursuit of self-interest in a freely operating labor market” (Heery, 2016, p. 4). Budd and Bhave’s (2008) unitarist perspective promotes that “the workers’ interests reside in a need for fulfillment at work or identification with a workplace community” (Heery, 2016, p. 4). While the pluralist perspective, “emphasizes a desire for equity and voice” (Heery, 2016, p. 4). Their critical perspective, equivalent to the radical frame, is divided into 3 distinct areas: Marxist, feminist, and race-based perspectives; that “challenges subordination and seeks to secure greater power and control over their working lives; and identifies an increasing recognition of fundamental divisions of interest among workers” (Heery, 2016, p.4). “The feminist perspective is based on the identification of gendered interests at work and the need to challenge the subordination of women to the patriarchal interests” (Heery, 2016, p. 4). The critical race perspective emphasizes “the need to challenge the subordination of minority groups” (Heery, 2016, p. 4).

Transnational Model of Organizations

According to Mintzberg (1972), “organizational structure is the framework of the relations on jobs, systems, operating processes, people and groups making efforts to achieve the goals' ' (Ahmady, Mehrpour, & Nikooravesh, 2016). The structure determines the way that people work; the arrangement of job and work processes; the collaborative efforts of the workforce members; the order for decision-making, power, and authority; and mechanisms for controlling the exchange of communication and information (Gutterman, 2013). Whereas the framework, functions, and mechanisms of organizational structures are being influenced by technological changes; there is minimal systematic knowledge of whether or how this technology has altered structural patterns or conditions that may lead to changes thereof (Tolbert & Hall, 2009; Zeller, 2017).

Moreover, the global market is expanding and changing business practices. The relative position of those

business practices is influenced by the spatial dimensions; of which the geographical location is preeminent (Ford, Gadde, Håkansson, Snehota, & Waluszewski, 2008). For instance, Lounsbury (2007) found that the structure and strategic objectives of an organization are influenced by geographic proximity (Marquis & Battilana, 2007). Tsai (2010) found that regional influences can begin from informal ‘bottom-up’ processes that grow into formal processes; thus, creating change in the formal organizational structure (Bathelt & Glückler, 2014). The issue is that “business practices in one market are dependent upon business practices in other markets”; therefore, adaptability in the organization’s structure may be required (Anderssohn & Mattsson, 2014, p. 7; Zeller, 2017).

Contingency Theorists, Lawrence and Lorsch (1967), integration is “the process of achieving unity of effort”; and differentiation is “the state of segmentation of the organizational systems into subsystems” (pp. 1-30). Their theory, frequently referred to as structural contingency theory, is applied in most studies to “characterize the organization in structural terms” with regards to their environment (Foss & Saebi, 2015, p. 90). The underlying processes and the informal systems through which work actually gets done is not a priority (Foss & Saebi, 2015). However, researchers, Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012), recognize the importance of structure and the influences of business processes. Their methodology addresses the resulting mismatch between processes and structure with “activities by phases and functions and tools” that are categorized to identify “the organizational structure of a company that is needed to perform its business processes well” (pp. 5413, 5411).

The transnational model, selected for this analytical paper, initially adopted a sequential view; where scale advantages were realized by “relocating production”; allowing the ability to face competitors with a global view rather than a multidomestic one (Hedlund, 1993, p. 3). On the other hand, in doing so, transnational organizations found that, “in a number of areas”, they had to adopt a geocentric or in Bartlett’s (1986) words, a ‘coordinated network’ view (Hedlund, 1993, p. 3).

Bartlett and Ghoshal’s (1989) transnational model promotes the practice of information and knowledge sharing. It also recognizes the benefits gained from local responsiveness and adaptation, an understanding of the local region is required. Essentially, “the key philosophy of a transnational model is adaptation to all environmental situations and achieving flexibility by capitalizing on knowledge flows (which take the form of decisions and value-added information) and two-way communication throughout the organization” (Reference for Business, n.d.). In *Managing Across Borders* (1998), Bartlett and Ghoshal argued that global expansion will require a transnational model, “which is based on an ‘integrated network’ of plants sharing expertise and knowledge with each other” (Edwards, 2004, p. 391).

Realistically, due to government regulations and cultural differences, globalization and “the use of a global strategy” for a global market is not global; actually, it is a market of many regions with dynamic “intra-regional economic activity” (Rugman, 2005, p. 2). Furthermore, the structure will need to continually adapt to the external business environment and the internal organization demands (Jeston & Nelis, 2008, p.194; Zeller, 2017). The current trend is to acknowledge that there is no ‘one-size-fits-all’ structure that will

accommodate an organization's multilayered obligation to meet strategic goals (Soyka, 2012, p. 153). More recently, organizations have morphed into a flexible, adaptable structure that includes a hybrid (traditional physical office / virtual off-site) workforce where the local region may be covered by employees located throughout numerous geographic regions and boundaries.

The Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional 'Brick and Mortar' Office) Workforce

According to conclusions drawn from a November, 2003 internal study conducted by Intel, "wireless mobility changes the way employees work"; e.g. the internal organization demands in relation to the external business environment (McLennan, 2008, p. 175; Zeller, 2017). The "Intuit 2020 Report, Twenty Trends that will Shape the Next Decade" noted that "the brick-and-mortar office will be a thing of the past, as the where and how people work and do business will change due to emerging Internet cloud and mobile technologies. Working in the cloud will increasingly shift work lives away from corporate offices altogether and toward an in-my-own-place, on-my-own-time work regimen" (Intuit, 2020; Zeller, 2018). Hence, Gandossy, Tucker, and Verma (2006) "observe, in the coming years, organizations will confront challenges related to demographic trends, global mobility, diversity, work/life issues, technology changes and a virtual workforce" (Rotich, 2015, p. 70; Zeller, 2019).

Another challenge is that collaboration and knowledge-sharing remains a key issue in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce (Zeller, Fall 2018). Transmitting knowledge from a traditional workforce to a virtual workforce will be complicated by known issues in the virtual environment; i.e. time zone differences, challenges in team building due to the depersonalized nature of online communication, misinterpretations of electronic messages, and so on. In the virtual world, this means selecting appropriate tools for communication, developing a strategy for following-up on communication, and adhering to guidelines (Montero & Montero, 2010, p. 13; Zeller, n.d.). Nonetheless, particularly in online collaboration, different interpretations are likely to occur; thereby, influencing knowledge sharing. Moreover, workers are likely to be hesitant to express their views on "electronic knowledge exchange forums" that are visible to management; possibly, inhibiting the exchange of information (Hislop, 2013, p. 141).

Furthermore, changes in work policies, such as for a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce, affect the organization and coordination of the activities; e.g. managing how and where work is done. To complicate matters, in the transnational organization, managing the policy change requires coordination across multiple regions. Today, whether the workplace is a virtual work-from-home setting or a traditional 'brick and mortar' office, the workforce is scattered. Wayne Turmel, co-founder of the Remote Leadership Institute, which helps managers deal with a scattered workforce, said many companies expanded working from home options for financial reasons; however, they don't adjust their remote work approach to balance remote work with collaboration (Lee, 2016; Zeller, Fall 2018)..

Nevertheless, there are benefits derived from creating traditional and virtual teams; e.g. collaboration between multiple functioning units. A number of research results identify improved communication and information flow, a better understanding of issues, and interdependencies between units. On the other hand, whereas some results indicate that the dynamics will "foster knowledge transfer and organizational learning"; others find that spatial dimensions may have a negative effect (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007, p. 50; Zeller, n.d.).

Organizational Learning

Peter Senge (1990) in his renowned book, *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization* (1990) catapulted the term ‘learning organization’ into a prominent position (Smith, 2001, 2007). Since then, several definitions for ‘learning organization’ have been developed. For example, Senge (1990) describes the learning organization as an “organization where people continually expand their capacity to create the results they truly desire, where new and expansive patterns of thinking are nurtured, where collective aspiration is set free, and where people are continually learning to see the whole together” (Smith, 2001, 2007). Primarily, the flexibility inherent to the context of a learning organization encourages continual adaptability to the market.

Pedler, Burgoyne, and Boydell (1997) “define the learning organization as an organization which facilitates the learning of all its members and consciously transforms itself and its context” (Hislop, 2013, p. 90). The definition emphasizes a “mutual, positive energy between the organizational context and the learning of its members” (Hislop, 2013, p. 90). These dynamics facilitate continual learning; subsequently “sustaining and contributing to the ongoing transformation of the organizational context” (Hislop, 2013, p. 90).

“Whereas learning in organizations can be characterized as involving a dynamic reciprocity between learning processes at the individual, group, and organizational level”; the learning at the organizational level “only occurs when learning at the individual or group level impacts on organizational-level processes and structures” (Hislop, 2013, p.87). On the other hand, according to Crossan, Lane, and White (1999), “learning that has become institutionalized at the organizational level is often difficult to change”; thus, creating competency traps where changes in internal and external environments are not recognized (Hislop, 2013, p. 88).

Academic researchers, such as Coopey (1995, 1998) and Contu and Willmott (2003), challenge that there are contradictions regarding the “power and authority of management” that are not addressed (Hislop, 2009, p. 93). This perspective of organizational learning recognizes that the “organization’s socially-based control systems that are used to create value alignment around the benefits to all of learning, has the potential to reinforce management power, and contradict the logic of emancipation embodied in the organizational learning rhetoric” (Hislop, 2009, p. 96). Due to the power structure in the employment relationship, which places “workers in a subordinate position to management”, the learning organization described in the prescriptive approach “is unlikely to be achieved” (Hislop, 2009, p. 93, 94). In fact, the managerial approach is a significant factor in literature on organizational learning as learning is considered to be “an organizational activity that can and should be managed in order to improve organizational performance” (Huysman, 2000, p. 89). That is, management approaches learning from this “active agency standpoint”; i.e. learning is one-directed where individuals learn from their environment (Huysman, 2000, p. 89).

Per Bunderson and Reagans (2011), the proponents of the learning organization do not adequately take into account “power, politics, and conflict” (Hislop, 2013, p. 94). In essence, the relevance thereof in the “analysis of learning processes” is overlooked (Hislop, 2013, p. 94). Primarily, there are 3 interrelated factors: (1) Power-Knowledge: “the precise way that the power-knowledge relationship is understood depends on how power is conceptualized”; (2) Power-Employment Relationship: “the embeddedness of power in the employment relationship”; (3) Power / Politics-Lack of Value Consensus: “potential for conflict and disagreement that this creates” (Hislop, 2013, pp.94-5).

Accordingly, Meriläinen and Tiernari (2001) propose that organizational learning literature does an inadequate job of addressing power relations; “as well as for the consequences of learning for gender, age and race or ethnicity” (Raaijmakers, Bleijenbergh, Fokkinga, & Visser, n.d., p. 2). A key component of sense-making and learning is “identity construction”; thus, the cultural stereotypes contribute to their “disparate treatment” (Wasik, 2015, p. 5). Essentially, the socially constructed roles of men and women in organizations “influences the learning process in the workplace” (Wasik, 2015, Abstract). “Some norms, especially those related to gender roles, are particularly ‘sticky’” (Wasik, 2015, p. 11).

Summation of the Findings and Suggested Framework for Future Research

In an analytical paper, the author poses a question, collects relevant data from other researchers, analyzes the data from their viewpoints, then *concludes with a summation of findings and a suggested framework for further study* (Paper Pile, 2020; Personal Writer, 2008). The author maintains a neutral position; the focal point is “the findings and conclusions of other researchers” (Paper Pile, 2020).

The questions posed for this analytical paper are: What is the relationship, if any, between global employee relations and organizational learning? Is that relationship being redefined by the increase in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce in the transnational organization? The conceptual framework is the United States-based transnational models of multinational organizations with a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce.

Summation of the Findings.

A perspective is defined as a way of looking at something, not the thing itself; e.g. it is not the system or form of organization. In essence, frames of reference or perspectives are complex formulations that, on one hand, apply a qualitative method resting on underlying assumptions about the interest of workers and their employers, which give rise to formal ideologies. They are based on normative positions for evaluating the present and shaping the future. On the other hand, they generate theoretical models of the employment relationship, which offer explanations of institutions, behaviors, and outcomes, that can be weighed and tested through empirical research.

The frames of reference, or employee relations perspectives as they are more commonly referred to, were first identified in 1966, by Alan Fox. The perspectives, (1) unitarist, no conflict of interest between those supplying financial capital and their representatives, and those contributing their labor and skills on the other; (2) pluralist, accepts conflict as inevitable but containable through various institutional arrangements; and (3) the radical or Marxist perspective, reconciles those who are exploited to their condition, while leaving the structured inequality at the heart of the employment relationship unchanged; continue to be a factor in a number of disciplines as a foundation for explaining the the needs, wants, and aspirations of employees, employers, and the state--and the degree to which these interests are compatible.

Since then, additional perspectives, some rebelling against the original frames of references; while others represent subdivisions, combinations; and entirely new perspectives; have been created. For instance, Godard

(2000) presents a managerialist viewpoint of the unitary perspective as well as the neoclassical or neo-conservative perspectives to align worker and employer interests through market processes and economic incentives. Budd and Bhava (2008), isolate the constituents in the employment relationship in their four frames of reference: (1) egoist, the pursuit of self-interest in a freely operating labor market secures beneficial outcomes, the maximization of utility; (2) unitarist, the workers' interests reside in a need for fulfillment at work or identification with a workplace community;. (3) pluralist, emphasizes a desire for equity and voice; and (4) critical, equivalent to the radical frame, is divided into 3 distinct areas that indicate an increasing recognition of fundamental divisions of interest among workers: Marxist, feminist, and race-based perspectives.

Moreover, the model of the organization imposes its own methods to aligning the interests of employees, employers, and the state. In 1998, Bartlett and Ghoshal argued that global expansion will require a transnational model, which is based on an 'integrated network' of plants sharing expertise and knowledge with each other. In addition, organizational structures have been influenced by the increase in the hybrid (traditional physical office / virtual off-site) workforce. Currently, organizations are confronted with challenges related to demographic trends, global mobility, diversity, work/life issues, technology changes and a virtual workforce that affect the organization and coordination of the activities; e.g. managing how and where work is done, In this case, Budd and Bhava's (2008) unitarist perspective can help to identify where and how there are changes, particularly regarding the virtual workers' interests, fulfill their need at work or identification with a workplace community,

Fox's radical or Marxist perspective, which reconciles those who are exploited to their condition, while leaving the structured inequality at the heart of the employment relationship unchanged; continues to be a factor in a number of disciplines as a foundation for explaining the the needs, wants, and aspirations of employees, employers, and the state--and the degree to which these interests are compatible. Though the radical or Marxist perspective leaves the employment relationship unchanged, the crux of the matter is to identify if and how the changing needs, wants, and aspirations introduced by the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce are influencing that employment relationship.

Whereas some results indicate that the dynamics of a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce will foster knowledge transfer and organizational learning; others find that spatial dimensions may have a negative effect. Notably, learning at the organizational level only occurs when learning at the individual or group level impacts on organizational-level processes and structures. Conversely, learning that has become institutionalized at the organizational level is often difficult to change; thus, creating competency traps where changes in internal and external environments are not recognized. A contributing factor is that the proponents of the learning organization do not adequately take into account power, politics, and conflict; e.g. (1) Power-Knowledge: the precise way that the power-knowledge relationship is understood depends on how power is conceptualized; (2) Power-Employment Relationship: the embeddedness of power in the employment relationship; (3) Power / Politics-Lack of Value Consensus: potential for conflict and disagreement that this creates.

Accordingly, the managerial approach is a significant factor in literature on organizational learning as learning is considered to be an organizational activity that can and should be managed in order to improve organizational performance. That is, management approaches learning from this active agency standpoint; i.e. learning is one-directed

where individuals learn from their environment. Power, politics, and conflict are particularly evident in online collaboration, where workers are likely to be hesitant to express their views on electronic knowledge exchange forums that are visible to management; possibly, inhibiting the exchange of information. Fox's pluralist, accepts conflict as inevitable but containable through various institutional arrangements; Budd and Bhawe (2008), pluralist perspective emphasizes a desire for equity and voice, isolates the constituents in the employment relationship..

In summary, one part of the equation is formulated by the perspective; the basis for which may rely on a homogenized or isolated constituent view of the workforce; or is viewed through the lens of management, economics or the market. The other part is to understand new and changing regulations and polycentric practices of a global market and economy. However, a global market and economy are not actually global; realistically, they are a market of many regions with dynamic intra-regional economic activity, government regulations, and cultures. In this mix, organizations will confront challenges related to demographic trends, global mobility, diversity, work/life issues, technology changes and a virtual workforce. Furthermore, the effect of the power structure; e.g. management, on organizational learning remains a key issue; particularly with regards to the changing dynamics of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce. Primarily, the interest of workers and their employers is varied and complex; any one of which can be used to formulate normative positions or to test theories through empirical research for evaluating the present and shaping the future that, in turn, lead to formal ideologies to guide employee relations.

Suggested Frameworks for Future Studies.

Methodology:

Richard Hyman "asserts that to discover some statistical association between variables does not entail either the development or testing of theory, and by implication, he suggests that **qualitative research** focused on processes and meaning would prove more illuminating. Societal phenomena must be analyzed in terms of actually existing structures and causal mechanisms that are not necessarily directly observable (and hence quantifiable)--a conviction which is, of course, a major challenge to the principles of empiricism and quantification" (Frege, Kelly, & McGovern, 2011, p. 216).

Furthermore, Hyman's "firm and longstanding insistence on the need for cross-national comparative research is being increasingly accepted as conventional wisdom among researchers. Moreover, at a time when quantitative research has become increasingly fashionable, Hyman has positioned himself as an articulate and influential proponent of qualitative research and of what some researchers describe as 'contextualized comparisons'" (Frege, Kelly, & McGovern, 2011, p. 225).

Cross-National Comparative Research: (Excerpt from Zeller, 2017, Sept).

As firms expand into other countries, national issues, such as government involvement and unions, may add complexity to the introduction of home country employee relations in a host country (Edwards, 2004, p. 390). Thus, there are underlying variables; i.e., the political, legal, and institutional contexts of the home and host countries, that may influence the results of any study.

From a global perspective, when changes to the business processes influenced by the hybrid workforce do change structure; off-shore facilities may be faced with additional roadblocks. For instance, in Germany, the Worker's Council must approve all decisions that affect the workforce before being implemented (Jeston & Nelis, 2008b). Nevertheless, even in Hofstede's renowned study of IBM's strong corporate culture, variations of the legacy were evident (Edwards, 2004, p. 392). Thus, transferring the corporate culture may not be full-proof; thereby, allowing for variations throughout the organizational structure.

The positive element to the effects of off-shore regulations is that "organizations can benefit from best practices from around the world" (Jeston & Nelis, 2008b, p. 115). However, incorporating those best practices, including through the lens of a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') workforce, requires assessing business processes and structural changes in that light (p. 115). Furthermore, whether the home country's 'best way' of operations is seen as "innovative, a model to be imitated, or as a deviant" may be dependent on the relationships between home and host countries, the relative reasons for integrated international operations, and the firm's power to direct their investments toward their preferred employment systems (Almond, Edwards, & Clark, 2003, pp. 434-5).

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